

PROFILE OF CRIMES PERPETRATED BY DELINQUENT MINORS IN SRINAGAR KASHMIR

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Introduction

Juvenile is defined as a person who has not completed the age of 18 years. In recent times there has been increase in number of crimes committed by juveniles. It is largely attributed to the mental, social, psychological and physical development occurring during this period. The criminal tendency in youngsters must therefore, be timely curbed so that they do not turn into habitual criminals in their future life.

Objectives

1. To study the profile of crimes committed by juveniles.
2. To assess various factors associated with juvenile delinquency.

Methodology:

Research Design: - Observational study

Study setting: Randomly selected juvenile home in Srinagar, Kashmir

Study Subjects: All Juveniles inhabiting at juvenile home Srinagar fulfilling our inclusion criteria

Study Duration: Two months i.e. between January- June 2021

Sample Size: Absolute sampling.

Data collection: A proforma was prepared, and finalized. Juvenile home/children home/specialhome was visited. Records were acquired after obtaining permission from the concerned authority. Subjects/ cases were interviewed by one on one technique and the scope of study was be explained.

Data Analysis:

Data analysis was done by using SPSS 20.0 statistical software. Qualitative data was expressed by using frequency and percentage.

Results:

A total 52 cases fulfilling our inclusion criteria were considered in our study.

Of total 52 cases studied, 48 were males and 4 were females depicting an absolute male prepondance

Table 1. Sociodemographic profile of cases (n=52)

Variable	NO.OF CASES	PERCENTAGE (%)
Age		
13-15	11	21
16-18	41	79
Socioeconomic status		
I	4	8
II	4	8
III	7	13
IV	17	33

V	20	38
Family type (Broken)		
Yes	30	58
No	22	42

The current study revealed that majority of the juveniles who committed crimes belonged to the Socioeconomic class V (38%) followed by those who belonged to socioeconomic class IV (33%).

Fig 1. Pattern of crimes committed by Juveniles

Majority (28) of the juveniles had committed law and order violations in form of stone pelting on law enforcing agencies or were involved in other anti-national activities. The second major crime committed by juveniles was in form of theft (12). Substance abuse was noticed in 8 juveniles who had committed crimes.

Conclusion

India is increasing in the rate of juvenile crimes and it is a serious concern for the Nation and solutions to end this problem need to be sought carefully. Total 52 Juveniles inhabiting at juvenile homes Srinagar were included in the study. Lower socioeconomic class and age of committing crimes has a significant relationship with committing crimes.

REFERENCES

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